

Effect of Training and HR Development on Employee Performance with Motivation as an Intervening Variable in PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Ido Nurzaini Aziz *, Djoko Setyo Widodo and Iwan Kurniawan Subagja

Universitas Krisnadwipayana Jakarta Campus Unkris Jatiwaringin PO BOX 7774/Jat Cm Jakarta 13077, Indonesia.

Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances, 2021, 06(02), 169–181

Publication history: Received on 21 January 2021; revised on 24 February 2021; accepted on 26 February 2021

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2021.6.2.0032>

Abstract

This study aims to: 1) to test and analyze the effect of training on motivation, 2) the effect of HR development on motivation, 3) to test and analyze the effect of training on employee performance 4) to test and analyze the effect of HR development on employee performance 5) to test and analyze the effect of motivation on employee performance 6) to test and analyze the effect of training on employee performance through motivation, 7) to test and analyze the effect of HR development on employee performance through motivation.

This research was conducted at PT. Rekasis Gigatama with a sample of 81 respondents. The sampling technique uses a random sampling technique. The data analysis method uses descriptive analysis and path analysis.

The results showed that: 1) there was an effect of training on motivation 2) there was an effect on HR development on motivation 3) there was an effect on training on employee performance 4) there was an influence on HR development on employee performance 5) there was an influence on motivation on employee performance 6) no influence training on employee performance through motivation, and 7) there is an influence of HR development on employee performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama through motivation.

Keywords: Training; HR development; Motivation; Employee performance

1. Introduction

The intense competition in the business world due to this globalization also impacts the certainty that companies are faced with various challenges to make their companies exist in the face of dynamic changes in change, where companies must have the advantage to win the competition.

Noe et al (2008) stated that currently several challenges must be faced by companies, namely "advances in technology, globalization, and sustainable demands". Meanwhile, Dessler (2010) argues that there are challenges in different forms: "labor diversity, service society trends, and horizontal organization."

In the old paradigm, the strength of a country or company is measured by the amount of ownership of natural resources, the new paradigm gives rise to competitive power supported by the superiority of the most important resource, namely human resources. Currently, the company's performance will certainly not be achieved optimally if it is not supported by human resources, who can provide maximum results along with other resources owned by the company.

* Corresponding author: Ido Nurzaini Aziz

Universitas Krisnadwipayana Jakarta Campus Unkris Jatiwaringin PO BOX 7774/Jat Cm Jakarta 13077, Indonesia.

Employee performance is the result obtained by employees, which in quality and quantity is achieved and acquired by employees as a measure to be able to get or achieve the desired results. According to Griffin (2013), performance is one of the total collections of available work to workers. Meanwhile, according to Hersey and Blanchard (1993), performance is a function of motivation and ability. To complete a task or job, a person must have a certain degree of willingness and level of ability. Someone's willingness and skills are not effective enough to do something without a clear understanding of what to do and how to do it by other researchers. Donnelly et al., (1994) suggest that the notion of performance refers to the level of success in carrying out tasks and achieving predetermined goals. Performance is declared good and successful if the desired goals can be adequately achieved.

Companies need employees who can make positive contributions according to the competencies they have at their respective work posts as required. Companies must continuously improve their employees' competence through various training that has a positive effect on improving company performance through motivation to work better and be more disciplined. Be faster, more professional, and have the integrity and commitment to achieving the company's vision and mission to achieve the target success rate set. Efforts to improve employee performance are a formidable challenge for management, such is the strategic position of human resources because improving company performance depends on the performance of its human resources.

In this study, it is explained that training is seen as a means of overcoming changes that are technological innovation, market competition and plays a key role in improving employee performance, so if the training carried out by the company is successful. Employee performance will increase accordingly. According to Hamalik (2010), Training is a series of processes that include actions (efforts) that are carried out deliberately in the form of assisting workers carried out by professional coaching workers in a unit of time which aims to improve the workability of participants in certain fields of work in order to increase effectiveness and productivity in an organization. According to Denim (2008: 43), training is a learning technique that involves individual observation of work and determining feedback to improve performance or correct errors. Training is intended to enhance the mastery of various skills and methods for carrying out specific, detailed and routine work, training prepares employees to do current jobs (Handoko, 2004).

Apart from training, a factor that influences employee performance is the development of employee human resources. Human resource development is "a continuous effort to improve the quality of human resources in the broadest sense, through education, training and coaching" (Silalahi, 2000: 249). And development is "the preparation of individuals to take on different or higher responsibilities in the organization" (Simamora, 2008: 273).

Development usually relates to increased intellectual or emotional abilities needed to fit into better work. Development rests on the fact that an employee will need to develop knowledge, skills, and abilities in order to work well in a succession of positions that have been served during his career. The long-term career preparation of an employee for a series of positions is what employee development means. And the quality and quantity of human resources determine whether or not the goals/objectives of an organization or company are achieved. The higher the knowledge and ability/expertise of human resources in a company, the higher the company's ability to win the competition, the more aligned the HR management and development strategy of human resources with the company's strategy, the higher the probability of the company's success in realizing the company's vision and mission.

One other effort to improve employee performance is by providing motivation. Motivation and performance are two elements that are constructive and correlative. Both of them are mutually conditional and cannot be separated from the other. Employee work performance will below if they do not have the motivation to carry out the job. Conversely, if the employee has a high motivation to carry out the job, generally, the employee's performance level will be increased. According to Kadarisman (2012), work motivation is a driving force or impetus in a person to want to behave and work actively and well following the duties and obligations that have been given to him.

1.1. Literature review

1.1.1. Training

Development usually relates to increased intellectual or emotional abilities needed to fit into better work. Development rests on the fact that an employee will need to develop knowledge, skills, and abilities in order to work well in a succession of positions that have been served during his career. The long-term career preparation of an employee for a series of positions is what employee development means. And the quality and quantity of human resources determines whether or not the goals/objectives of an organization or company are achieved. The higher the knowledge and ability/expertise of human resources in a company, the higher the company's ability to win the competition, the more aligned the HR management and development strategy of human resources with the company's strategy, the higher the probability of the company's success in realizing the company's vision and mission.

One other effort to improve employee performance is by providing motivation. Motivation and performance are two elements that are constructive and correlative. Both of them are mutually conditional and cannot be separated from the other. Employee work performance will be low if they do not have the motivation to carry out the job. Conversely, if the employee has a high motivation to carry out the job, generally, the employee's performance level will be increased. According to Kadarisman (2012), work motivation is a driving force or impetus in a person to want to behave and work actively and well following the duties and obligations that have been given to him.

1.1.2. Human Resource Development

Human resource development is "a continuous effort to improve the quality of human resources in the broadest sense, through education, training and coaching" (Silalahi, 2000: 249). And development is "the preparation of individuals to assume different or higher responsibilities in the organization" (Simamora, 2009: 273).

Development is "an effective way to meet some of the challenges faced by many large organizations". These challenges include employee obsolescence, socio-technical changes and workforce turnover. The ability to overcome these challenges is a determining factor for the personnel department's success in maintaining effective human resources (Handoko, 2008: 117).

Development usually relates to increased intellectual or emotional abilities needed to fit into better work. Development rests on the fact that an employee will need to develop knowledge, skills, and abilities in order to work well in a succession of positions that have been served during his career. The long-term career preparation of an employee for a series of positions is what employee development means.

Development has a broader scope. Development is more focused on the general long-term needs of the organization. The results are indirect and can only be measured in the long term. Development also helps employees prepare for changes in their jobs that can result from new technology, job designs, new customers, or new product markets.

Employee development benefits are felt to be increasingly important due to job demands or positions, as a result of technological advances and increasingly intense competition among similar companies. Every company personnel is required to work effectively and efficiently so that the quality and quantity of work can be better so that the company's competitiveness is getting bigger. This development is carried out for non-career purposes as well as for employees through training and education.

A good measuring indicator should have several indicators. The human resource development indicators according to Hasibuan (2012: 82) are measured from the development method applied, including the following: Employee performance, employee discipline, employee attendance, levels of production damage, tools and machines, employee accident rates, waste levels of materials standards, labor and time, Level of Cooperation, Level of Employee Intensive Wages, Employee Initiatives and Leadership and leadership decisions.

1.1.3. Motivation

The term motivation comes from the Latin word *movere*, which means "to move". Robbins et al (2007: 1) formulate "motivation as a willingness to carry out high efforts to achieve organizational goals conditioned by the ability to fulfill certain individual needs". Thoha (2015: 206) says that human behavior is essentially goal-oriented in other words that a person's behavior is generally stimulated by the desire to achieve several goals. Motivation, this term is sometimes used interchangeably with other terms, such as need, desire, drive, enthusiasm or impulse.

According to Robbins (2007: 208), a process that produces an intensity, direction, and individual persistence to achieve one goal. In comparison, general motivation is concerned with the efforts towards each goal. According to Nimran and Amirullah (2011: 47), motivation is a condition in which one's efforts and willpower are directed towards achieving certain results. These results may take the form of: (a). Productivity; (b). The presence of creative work behavior.

Meanwhile, according to Adair (2007: 192), motivation makes people do something. Still, the more important meaning of this word is that motivation is what makes people try and expend energy for what they do. A simple definition of the word "motivation" might "get people to do what has to be done willingly and well."

Winardi (2007: 6) argues that: Motivation is a potential power that exists within a human being, which he can develop himself or be developed by several outside forces which essentially revolve around monetary rewards and non-monetary rewards, which can affect the results of their performance positive or negative, which depends on the situation and conditions faced by the person concerned.

From some of the definitions above, the theoretical basis used in this study is the opinion of Thoha (2015: 206), saying that human behavior is essentially goal-oriented in other words that a person's behavior is generally stimulated by the desire to achieve several goals. Motivation, this term is sometimes used interchangeably with other terms, such as needs, wants, encouragement, enthusiasm, or impulse.

This study uses McClelland's concept in Mangkunegara (2014: 94) because it focuses on three employee needs that the organization must meet. The need factor is then derived into indicators to determine the level of employees' work motivation, namely: Need for achievement, need for strength, and need for relationships.

1.1.4. Employee Performance

Performance is "the result of a job performed during a certain period which can be measured by the quality and quantity produced". Performance is not an individual characteristic, such as talent or ability, but results from the manifestation of that talent or ability itself. Performance is a manifestation of ability in the form of real work.

According to Sinambela (2012: 480) states that employee performance is defined "as the ability of employees to do certain skills". According to Mangkunegara (2014: 67), the definition of performance is "the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to him".

From the descriptions of the three experts, it can be concluded that performance is workability performed by an employee, as well as carrying out the duties and responsibilities assigned by the company. The following is a description of indicators that indicate the achievement of a target or objective that has been agreed and set. A job can be measured through 6 dimensions, namely: budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together.

2. Research Methods

2.1. Research Sites

The observation unit of this research is the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama which is located at the Office Complex, Letnan Sugiyono BSD, South Tangerang.

2.2. Research Design

This study uses an explanatory research approach, namely "research that explains causal relationships and tests the relationship between several variables through testing or explanatory research" (Singarimbun and Effendi, 2002). So in this study, every variable that is presented in the hypothesis will be observed by testing the causal relationship of the independent variable to the dependent variable.

Figure 1 Framework

2.3. Population and Sample

In this study, the population taken was all permanent employees at the office and workshop of PT. Rekasis Gigatama, which currently numbered 430 people. The sample "is part of the number and characteristics of the population"

(Sugiyono, 2016: 62). From the existing population, to determine the minimum sample size is obtained using the Slovin formula. In contrast, the sampling technique used by researchers in this study is the Proportional Random Sampling technique, which is to take a sample in each area determined to be balanced or proportional to the number of objects in each area carried out randomly (Arikunto, 2006). In this study, the population numbered 430 people. The number of samples as the object of observation was 81 respondents. This number is considered representative or represents the population.

2.4. Types and Sources of Data

Data is "something that is used or needed in research using certain predetermined parameters" (Priyatno, 2008). Something in question is factual information. Algifari (2011) defines data, namely "information that has been processed into tables or graphs". The information itself is the result of the data collection methods used in the research (Algifari, 2011). Thus it can be concluded that data is something very useful for researchers, especially in the research process, and can support research results. This study's types of data (Priyatno, 2008) are qualitative data and quantitative data.

2.5. Data Analysis Techniques

This research is a quantitative study with path analysis. Quantitative analysis, which is a method of analysis with quantifiable and quantifiable numbers, and in the process using statistical tools. Statistics themselves are scientific methods used to collect, process, analyze, and interpret data in the form of numbers, then conclude the data, where the data is presented in the form of tables, graphs, or images (Algifari, 2011). Path analysis is "a diagram connecting the independent, intermediate and dependent variables". The relationship pattern is shown using arrows. The single arrows show the causal relationship between the exogenous or intermediate variables and one or more dependent variables. The arrows also relate the error to all of the respective endogenous variables. The double arrows show the correlation between pairs of exogenous variables.

3. Results

3.1. Path Analysis

Figure 2 Path Analysis Equations (Source: Primary data processed, 2020)

3.2. The Effect of Training on Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

To determine the effect of training on motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama, it is necessary to use the t-test. The results showed that the training variable's t-count value was 2.013, while the t-table value was 1.664. Thus $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($2.013 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at the fundamental level. This suggests that training has an effect on motivation. Thus the first hypothesis is tested and proven.

3.3. The Influence of Human Resources Development on Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Table 19 shows that the t-count value of the HR development variable is 7.579, while the t-table value is 1.664. Thus $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($7.579 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at that real level. This concludes that HR development affects motivation. Thus the second hypothesis is tested and proven.

3.4. The Effect of Training on Employee Performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

To see the effect of training on employee performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama , it is necessary to use the t-test. The results showed that the training variable's t-count value was 3.053, while the t-table value was 1.664. Thus $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($3.053 > 1.664$.), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at this real level. This concludes that training affects employee performance. Thus the third hypothesis is tested and proven.

3.5. The Influence of Human Resources Development on Employee Performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

The results showed that the t-count value of the human resource development variable was 1.847, while the t-table value was 1.664. Thus $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($1.847 > 1.664$.), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at that real level. This concludes that HR development affects employee performance. Thus the fourth hypothesis is tested and proven.

3.6. The Effect of Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

The results showed that the t-count value of the motivation variable was 4.165, while the t-table value was 1.664. Thus $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($4.165 > 1.664$.), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at this real level. This concludes that motivation affects employee performance. Thus the fifth hypothesis is tested and proven.

3.7. The Effect of Training on Employee Performance through Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

$$X_1 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_1}) \times (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0,501 \times 0,417 = 0,209$$

The indirect effect's value is obtained from the path coefficient value $\rho_{x_3x_1}$ multiplied by the path coefficient value ρ_{yx_3} to $(0.501 \times 0.417) = 0.209$. These results indicate that the value of the indirect effect coefficient $\{(\rho_{x_3x_1}) \times (\rho_{yx_3})\}$ is smaller than the value of the direct effect coefficient ρ_{yx_1} , ($0.209 < 0.295$). This shows that motivation cannot mediate, namely training in influencing employee performance. Thus the sixth hypothesis is untested and unproven.

3.8. The Influence of Human Resources Development on Employee Performance Through Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

$$X_2 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_2}) \times (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0.829 \times 0.417 = 0.345$$

The indirect effect's value is obtained from the path coefficient value $\rho_{x_3x_2}$ multiplied by the path coefficient value ρ_{yx_3} to $(0.829 \times 0.417) = 0.345$. This result shows that the value of the indirect effect coefficient $\{(\rho_{x_3x_2}) \times (\rho_{yx_3})\}$ is greater than the value of the coefficient of direct influence ρ_{yx_2} , ($0.345 > 0.235$). This shows that motivation can mediate, namely training in influencing employee performance. Thus the seventh hypothesis is tested and proven.

3.9. Total Effect

- Effect of training on employee performance through motivation
- $X_1 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_1}) + (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0.209 + 0.417 = 0.626$
- The total effect of training on employee performance through motivation is 0.626.
- The influence of HR development on employee performance through motivation.
- $X_2 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_2}) + (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0.345 + 0.417 = 0.762$
- The total effect of human resource development on employee performance through motivation is 0.762
- Effect of training on employee performance
- $X_1 \rightarrow Y = \rho_{yx_1} = 0,501$
- The total effect of training on employee performance is 0.501.
- The influence of HR development on employee performance
- $X_2 \rightarrow Y = \rho_{yx_2} = 0.829$
- The total effect of HR development on employee performance is 0.829
- The influence of motivation on employee performance
- $X_3 \rightarrow Y = \rho_{yx_3} = 0.417$
- The total influence that arises from motivation on employee performance is 0.417
- The influence of the residual coefficient variable on the motivation coefficient $e_1 = 0.561$
- The influence of the residual coefficient variable on employee performance coefficient $e_2 = 0.493$

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Training on Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Training is an effort to reduce or eliminate the gap between employee abilities and what the organization wants. This effort is carried out by increasing employees' workability by increasing knowledge and skills and changing attitudes. Employees are the organization's most valuable assets because with all their potential, employees can continue to be trained and developed so that they are more efficient, their performance will be more optimal to achieve organizational goals. According to the opinion of Gomes (2003: 197), training is "every effort to improve the performance of workers in a particular job which is their responsibility, or a job that is related to their job."

The training variable is measured using five indicators: instructors, participants, materials, methods, and objectives. Each indicator consists of several statement items. Meanwhile, according to Adair (2007: 192), motivation is what makes people do something, but the more important meaning of this word is that motivation is what makes people try and expend energy for what they do. A simple definition of the word "motivation" might "get people to do what has to be done willingly and well." The motivation variable is measured using three indicators: need for achievement, need for strength and need for relationships.

Based on the results of the training description analysis shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that instructor indicators, participants, materials, methods, and objectives form the training variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of training variables are objective indicators, namely, participants who have attended the training are following the organization's needs, and there is a need for evaluation to match the development of training needs.

Based on the analysis of the description of the motivation variable, it shows that the employees of PT. The Rekasis Gigatama agrees that the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for relationships form the motivation variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of the motivation variable are indicators of the need for achievement, namely doing work with initiative and creatively in carrying out tasks to make it easier and the work is carried out according to procedures, systems, leadership, HR professionalism, and adequate work facilities.

Based on the path analysis results, the training has an impact on increasing the motivation of the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama. This study's results are in line with the results of previous studies conducted by Diansyah and Saepul (2017).

4.2. The Influence of Human Resources Development on Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Human resource development is "a continuous effort to improve the quality of human resources in the broadest sense, through education, training and guidance". And development is "the preparation of individuals to take on different or higher responsibilities in the organization" (Simamora, 2006: 273).

Development is "an effective way to meet some of the challenges faced by many large organizations". These challenges include employee obsolescence, socio-technical changes and workforce turnover. The ability to overcome these challenges is a determining factor for the personnel department's success in maintaining effective human resources (Handoko, 2008: 117).

Human resource development variables are measured using ten indicators: work performance, discipline, absenteeism, levels of damage to production, tools and machines, accident rates, waste levels of raw materials, labor and time, level of cooperation, level of intensive wages, employee initiative and leadership and leadership decisions.

According to Robbins (2014: 208), a process produces an intensity, direction and individual persistence to achieve one goal. While general motivation is concerned with the efforts towards each goal. According to Nimran and Amirullah (2011: 47), motivation is a condition in which one's efforts and willpower are directed towards achieving certain results. These results may take the form of: (a). Productivity; (b). The presence of creative work behavior. Meanwhile, according to Adair (2007: 192), motivation makes people do something, but the more important meaning of this word is that motivation is what makes people try and expend energy for what they do. A simple definition of the word "motivation" might "get people to do what has to be done willingly and well."

The results of the descriptive analysis of HR development show that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama record tends to agree that indicators of work performance, discipline, absenteeism, levels of damage to production, tools and

machines, accident rates, levels of waste of raw materials, labor and time, levels of cooperation, levels of intensive wages, employee initiative and leadership and decisions leadership forms the human resource development variable. Indicators that contribute to the formation of HR development variables are work performance indicators, namely HR development is carried out for the progress of the company and employees who excel are developed for the position of the company. Based on the analysis of the description of the motivation variable, it shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for relationships form the motivation variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of the motivation variable are indicators of the need for achievement, namely doing work with initiative and creatively in carrying out tasks to make it easier and the work is carried out according to procedures, systems, leadership HR professionalism, and adequate work facilities.

Based on the results of the path analysis, the development of human resources has an impact on increasing the motivation of employees PT. Rekasis Gigatama. This study's results are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Suyanto, Sapta, Sudja (2018).

4.3. The Effect of Training on Employee Performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

According to Sinambela (2016: 480) argues that employee performance is defined as "the ability of employees to do certain skills", while according to Priansa (2014: 269), performance is "the level of success of employees in completing their work", then according to Mangkunegara (2013: 67), the definition of performance is "the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities assigned to him".

Employee performance variables are measured using seven indicators: budget management, task implementation, service quality, work quantity, work quality, timeliness and cooperation ability.

Based on the results of the training description analysis shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that instructor indicators, participants, materials, methods, and objectives form the training variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of training variables are objective indicators, namely, participants who have attended the training are in accordance with the organization's needs, and there is a need for evaluation to match the development of training needs. The results of the analysis of the employee performance description show that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together form employee performance variables. An indicator that contributes to the formation of employee performance variables is an indicator of cooperation ability, namely employees having good cooperation so that it supports activities in the work team. Employees have high skills, so that they are very supportive of employees at work.

Based on the path analysis results, training has an impact on improving employee performance for employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Sulaefi (2017), Subroto (2018), Kahpi, Khurosaini, Suhendra (2017), Zukriah, Heryanto (2019), Siagian (2018), Salah (2016), and Nassazi (2013).

4.4. The Influence of Human Resources Development on Employee Performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

The results of the descriptive analysis of HR development show that the employees of PT. Gigatama's record tends to agree that indicators of work performance, discipline, absenteeism, levels of damage to production, tools and machines, accident rates, levels of waste of raw materials, labor and time, levels of cooperation, levels of intensive wages, employee initiative and leadership and decisions leadership forms the human resource development variable. Indicators that contribute to the formation of HR development variables are work performance indicators, namely HR development is carried out for the progress of the company and employees who excel are developed for the position of the company.

Based on the results of the analysis of employee performance descriptions, it shows that employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together form employee performance variables. An indicator that contributes to the formation of employee performance variables is an indicator of cooperation ability, namely employees have good cooperation so that it is very supportive of activities in the work team and employees have high skills so that they are very supportive of employees at work.

Based on the path analysis results, HR development has an impact on improving employee performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama . The results of this study are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Suyanto, Sapta, Sudja (2018), Sulaefi (2017), Siagian (2018), Manggis, Yuesti, Sapta (2018), Salah (2016).

4.5. The Influence of Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Based on the results of the analysis of employee performance descriptions, it shows that employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together form employee performance variables. An indicator that contributes to the formation of employee performance variables is an indicator of cooperation ability, namely employees have good cooperation so that it is very supportive of activities in the work team and employees have high abilities so that they are very supportive of employees at work.

Based on the results of the analysis of the description of the motivation variable, it shows that the employees of PT. The Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for relationships form the motivation variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of the motivation variable are indicators of the need for achievement, namely doing work with initiative and creatively in carrying out tasks to make it easier and the work is carried out according to procedures, systems, leadership HR professionalism, and adequate work facilities.

Based on the path analysis results, motivation has an impact on improving employee performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Subroto (2018), Kahpi, Khurosaini, Suhendra (2017), Siagian (2018), Pranoto, Suharto, Subagja., I., K., (2020).

4.6. The Effect of Training on Employee Performance Through Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Based on the results of the training description analysis shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that instructor indicators, participants, materials, methods, and objectives form the training variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of training variables are objective indicators, namely, participants who have attended the training are in accordance with the needs of the organization, and there is a need for evaluation to match the development of training needs.

Based on the results of the analysis of employee performance descriptions, it shows that employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together form employee performance variables. An indicator that contributes to the formation of employee performance variables is an indicator of cooperation ability, namely employees have good cooperation so that it is very supportive of activities in the work team and employees have high abilities so that they are very supportive of employees at work.

Based on the results of the analysis of the description of the motivation variable, it shows that the employees of PT. The Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for relationships form the motivation variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of the motivation variable are indicators of the need for achievement, namely doing work with initiative and creatively in carrying out tasks to make it easier and the work is carried out according to procedures, systems, leadership HR professionalism, and adequate work facilities.

Based on the results of the path analysis shows that training has no impact on improving employee performance through motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama . The results of this study are not in line with the results of previous studies conducted by Diansyah and Saepul (2017), Salah (2016), and Nassazi (2013).

4.7. The Influence of Human Resources Development on Employee Performance through Motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama

Based on the results of the description analysis of HR development, it shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama record tends to agree that indicators of work performance, discipline, absenteeism, levels of damage to production, tools and machines, accident rates, levels of waste of raw materials, labor and time, levels of cooperation, levels of intensive wages, employee initiative and leadership and decisions leadership forms the human resource development variable. Indicators that contribute to the formation of HR development variables are work performance indicators, namely HR development is carried out for the progress of the company and employees who excel are developed for the position of the company.

Based on the results of the analysis of employee performance descriptions, it shows that employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together form employee performance variables. An indicator that contributes to the formation of employee performance variables is an indicator of cooperation ability, namely employees have good

cooperation so that it is very supportive of activities in the work team. Employees have high skills so that they are very supportive of employees at work.

Based on the analysis of the description of the motivation variable, it shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for relationships form the motivation variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of the motivation variable are indicators of the need for achievement, namely doing work with initiative and creatively in carrying out tasks to make it easier and the work is carried out according to procedures, systems, leadership, HR professionalism, and adequate work facilities.

Based on the path analysis results, HR development has an impact on improving employee performance through motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama. The results of this study are in line with the results of previous research conducted by Manggis, Yuesti, Sapta (2018), Salah (2016).

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

Based on the results of research analysis and discussion, it can be concluded as follows:

Based on Description Analysis

- The training variable shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that instructor indicators, participants, materials, methods, and objectives form the training variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of training variables are objective indicators, namely, participants who have attended the training are in accordance with the needs of the organization, and there is a need for evaluation to match the development of training needs.
- The HR development variable shows that the employees of PT. Gigatama's record tends to agree that indicators of work performance, discipline, absenteeism, levels of damage to production, tools and machines, accident rates, levels of waste of raw materials, labor and time, levels of cooperation, levels of intensive wages, employee initiative and leadership and decisions leadership forms the human resource development variable. Indicators that contribute to the formation of HR development variables are work performance indicators, namely HR development is carried out for the progress of the company and employees who excel are developed for the position of the company.
- The motivation variable shows that the employees of PT. The Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that the need for achievement, the need for strength and the need for relationships form the motivation variables. Indicators that contribute to the formation of the motivation variable are indicators of the need for achievement, namely doing work with initiative and creatively in carrying out tasks to make it easier and the work is carried out according to procedures, systems, leadership HR professionalism, and adequate work facilities.
- The employee performance variable shows that the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama tends to agree that budget management, task execution, quality of service, quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness and ability to work together form employee performance variables. An indicator that contributes to the formation of employee performance variables is an indicator of cooperation ability, namely employees have good cooperation so that it is very supportive of activities in the work team and employees have high abilities so that they are very supportive of employees at work.

Based on Path Analysis

- The t-count value of the training variable is 2.013, while the t-table value is 1.664. Thus $t_{count} > t_{Table}$ ($2.013 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at the real level. This suggests that training affects motivation. Based on the path analysis results, the training has an impact on increasing the motivation of the employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama .
- The t-count value of the human resource development variable is 7.579, while the t-table value is 1.664. Thus $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($7.579 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at that real level. This concludes that HR development affects motivation. Based on the results of the path analysis, the development of human resources has an impact on increasing the motivation of PT employees. Rekasis Gigatama.
- The t-count value of the training variable is 3.053, while the t-table value is 1.664. Thus $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($3.053 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at this real level. This concludes that training affects employee performance. Based on the path analysis results, training has an impact on improving employee performance for employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama.
- The t-count value of the human resource development variable is 1.847, while the t-table value is 1.664. Thus $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($1.847 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at that real level. This concludes that

HR development affects employee performance. Based on the path analysis results, HR development has an impact on improving employee performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama.

- The t-count value of the motivation variable is 4.165, while the t-table value is 1.664. Thus $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($4.165 > 1.664$), Thus H_0 is rejected, and H_1 is accepted at this real level. This concludes that motivation affects employee performance. Based on the path analysis results, motivation has an impact on improving employee performance at PT. Rekasis Gigatama.
- The indirect effect's value is obtained from the path coefficient value ρ_{x3x1} multiplied by the path coefficient value ρ_{yx3} to $(0.501 \times 0.417) = 0.209$. These results indicate that the value of the indirect effect coefficient $\{(\rho_{x3x1}) \times (\rho_{yx3})\}$ is smaller than the value of the direct effect coefficient ρ_{yx1} , ($0.209 < 0.295$). This shows that motivation cannot mediate, namely training in influencing employee performance. Based on the path analysis results, training has no impact on improving employee performance through motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama.
- The indirect effect's value is obtained from the path coefficient value ρ_{x3x2} multiplied by the path coefficient value ρ_{yx3} to $(0.829 \times 0.417) = 0.345$. This result shows that the value of the indirect effect coefficient $\{(\rho_{x3x2}) \times (\rho_{yx3})\}$ is greater than the value of the coefficient of direct influence ρ_{yx2} , ($0.345 > 0.235$). This shows that motivation can mediate, namely training, in influencing employee performance. Based on the path analysis results, HR development has an impact on improving employee performance through motivation at PT. Rekasis Gigatama.

Suggestions

The research results can be used as input and consideration in development plans, human resource development management in managing training strategies, human resource development, motivation, and performance of employees of PT. Rekasis Gigatama by considering the following factors:

- PT. Rekasis Gigatama must consider the training variables, especially in the instructor indicators, which give the lowest score for the formation of training variables by paying attention to the type of training directed more at increasing one's ability through formal channels with an extended period according to competency needs and the training material provided can develop skills for employees in completing work.
- PT. Rekasis Gigatama must consider HR development variables, especially in the incentive wage level indicator, which gives the lowest value to the formation of HR development variables by paying attention to employees' wages according to government regulations and work incentives work results.
- PT. Rekasis Gigatama must consider the motivation variable, especially in need for strength indicator which gives the lowest score for the formation of the motivation variable by paying attention to the wages offered by employees according to government regulations and work incentives according to the work of employees to take the initiative and be creative in carrying out tasks so that it is easier to do accordingly. Procedures, systems, human resource leadership professionalism, and existing work facilities.
- PT. Rekasis Gigatama must consider employee performance variables, especially on the punctuality indicator, which gives the lowest score for the formation of employee performance variables. The work done by employees must be on time and schedule. If employees violate, they are given punishment.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Acknowledgments to D. Djoko Setyo Widodo and Dr. Iwan Kurniawan Subagja

Disclosure of conflict of interest

This article no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Noe RA, Hollenbeck JR, Gerhart B, Wright PM. Human Resource Management: Gaining A Competitive Advantage, New York: McGraw Hill. 2008. <https://www.mheducation.com/highered/product/human-resource-management-noe-hollenbeck/M9781260076844.html>
- [2] Dessler Gary. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Jakarta: Indeks. 2010. <https://onesearch.id/Author/Home?author=Gary+Dessler>

- [3] Moorhead, Gregory dan Ricky W. Griffin. Perilaku Organisasi. Jakarta: Salemba Empat. 2013.
<https://onesearch.id/Author/Home?author=Gregory+Moorhead%2C+Ricky+W.+Griffin>
- [4] Hersey, Paul, Blanchard, Kenneth H. Management for Organizational Behavior, Sixth Edition. Singapore: Prentice-Hall. 1993.
<https://www.amazon.co.uk/Management-Organizational-Behaviour-Utilizing-Resources/dp/0135488753>
- [5] Gibson, James L, John M. Ivancevich dan James H. Donnelly, Jr. Organisasi dan Manajemen. Perilaku, Struktur, Proses. Edisi keempat. Jakarta: Erlangga. 1994.
<https://onesearch.id/Author/Home?author=James+L.+Gibson%2C+John+M.+Ivancevich%2C+James+H.+Donnelly>
- [6] Hamalik Oemar. Proses Belajar Mengajar. Jakarta. PT Bumi Aksara. 2011. <http://opac.ut.ac.id/detail-opac?id=25615>
- [7] Handoko Hani. Manajemen Personalia dan Sumberdaya Manusia, Penerbit BPFE, Yogyakarta. 2004.
<http://repository.pelitabangsa.ac.id/xmlui/handle/123456789/1734>
- [8] Silalahi, Berneth. Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia. Jakarta: Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Manajemen LPMI. 2000.
<http://ejurnal.untag-smd.ac.id/index.php/AP/article/view/2977>
- [9] Simamora. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Yogyakarta: Adi Citra Karya Nusa. 2008.
<https://opac.perpusnas.go.id/DetailOpac.aspx?id=553197>
- [10] Kadarisman M. Manajemen kompensasi. Jakarta: Rajawali pers. 2012.
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=16373746292813964388&hl=en&oi=scholar>
- [11] Hasibuan H, Malayu SP. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Edisi Revisi Kedua, Penerbit BPFE-UGM, Yogyakarta. 2012. http://library.fip.uny.ac.id/opac/index.php?p=show_detail&id=2528
- [12] Robbins SP, Timothy AJ. Organizational Behavior, 12th edition, Prentice-Hall, New Jersey. 2007.
<https://www.amazon.com/Organizational-Behavior-12th-Stephen-Robbins/dp/0132431564>
- [13] Thoah M. Perilaku Organisasi: Konsep Dasar dan Implikasinya, Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada. 2015.
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=4239674500682587234&hl=en&oi=scholar>
- [14] Nimran Umar. Perilaku Organisasi. Surabaya: Citra Media. 2011.
https://scholar.google.co.id/scholar?hl=id&as_sdt=0.5&cluster=8950632940383349845
- [15] Adair, John. Cara Menumbuhkan Pemimpin 7 Prinsip Kunci Pengembangan Kepemimpinan Yang Efektif. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama. 2007. <https://opac.perpusnas.go.id/DetailOpac.aspx?id=425260>
- [16] Winardi. Manajemen Perilaku Organisasi. Jakarta: Prenada Media. 2007.
<https://onesearch.id/Author/Home?author=Prof.+Dr.+J.+Winardi%2C+SE>
- [17] AA. Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara. Manajemen Sumber daya Manusia Perusahaan. PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, Bandung. 2014. <https://onesearch.id/Author/Home?author=Anwar+Prabu+Mangkunegara>
- [18] Sinambela, Lijan. Kinerja Pegawai: Teori, Pengukuran dan Implikasi. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu. 2012.
<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/3c63/6b945e50c7375e463832a2d06de38d952cf7.pdf>
- [19] Mangkunegara Anwar Prabu. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya. 2016. <http://repository.pelitabangsa.ac.id/xmlui/handle/123456789/1721>
- [20] Singarimbun, Masri dan Sofian Effendi. Metode Penelitian Survei. Jakarta: LP3ES. 2002.
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=16937312561604176767&hl=en&oi=scholar>
- [21] Sugiyono. Cara Mudah untuk Menulis Skripsi, Tesis dan Disertasi. Bandung: Alfabeta. 2016.
<https://opac.perpusnas.go.id/DetailOpac.aspx?id=910512>
- [22] Arikunto S. Metode Penelitian Kualitatif. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara. 2006.
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=2408530812527205402&hl=en&oi=scholar>
- [23] Priyatno, Dewi. Mandiri Belajar SPSS - Bagi Mahasiswa dan Umum, Yogyakarta: MediaKom. 2008.
<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=16404179866686704095&hl=en&oi=scholar>
- [24] Algifari. Analisis Regresi, Teori, Kasus & Solusi. Yogyakarta: BPFE UGM. 2011.
https://scholar.google.co.id/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0.5&cluster=17057895750048068229

- [25] Gomes-Mejia, Luis R, David Balkin. Management People Performance Change. New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc Publishing as Prentice Hall. 2013. <https://www.worldcat.org/title/management-people-performance-change/oclc/1011182922>
- [26] Diansyah dan Tatang Saepul. Pengaruh Pelatihan Dan Kompensasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Dengan Motivasi sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Mikro Laju Cluster Jakarta 2 Pt. Bank Cimb Niaga Tbk. Media Studi Ekonomi. Januari – Juni 2017; 20(1). <http://journal.uta45jakarta.ac.id/index.php/MSE/article/view/769>
- [27] Suyanto, I Ketut Setia Sapta, I Nengah Sudja. The Effect of Career Development and Leadership on Employee Performance with Work Motivation as Intervening Variables on Cv. Blue Waters Bali. International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review. 2018; 9(3). <https://ijcr.info/index.php/ijcr/article/view/467>
- [28] Priansa, Donni Juni dan H. Suwanto. Manajemen Sumber daya Manusia Dalam Organisasi Publik dan Bisnis. Alfabeta. Bandung. 2011. <https://openlibrary.telkomuniversity.ac.id/home/catalog/id/10022/slug/manajemen-sdm-dalam-organisasi-publik-dan-bisnis.html>
- [29] Sulaefi. Pengaruh Pelatihan Dan Pengembangan Terhadap Disiplin Kerja Dan Kinerja Karyawan. Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan. 2017; 5(1). <http://jurnal.unmer.ac.id/index.php/jmdk/article/view/1212>
- [30] Setyowati Subroto. Pengaruh Pelatihan Dan Motivasi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. Jurnal Ekonomi dan Kewirausahaan. 2018; 12(1). <http://jurnal.unismabekasi.ac.id/index.php/optimal/article/view/1544>
- [31] Heri Sapari Kahpi, Aan Khurosaini, Indra Suhendra. Pengaruh Pelatihan Dan Motivasi Berprestasi Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dengan Kompetensi Sebagai Variabel Intervening. Jurnal Riset Bisnis dan Manajemen Tirtayasa. (JRBM), hh.1-9 Mei. 2017; 1(1). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343593563_Pengaruh_Pelatihan_dan_Motivasi_Berprestasi_Terdapat_Kinerja_Pegawai_Dengan_Kompetensi_Sebagai_Variabel_Intervening_Studi_Empiris_Pada_Pegawai_Perusahaan_Daerah_Air_Minum_Kabupaten_Lebak
- [32] Ammil Zukriah, Heryanto. The Effect of Work Motivation And Discipline on Employee Performance In HumSumatera With Education And Training As Variable Intervening. Archives of Business Research. 2019; (5). <https://journals.schog.org/index.php/ABR/article/view/6441>
- [33] Mauli Siagian. Effect of Leadership, Training, and Human Resources Competency to Employee Performance through Motivation As Intervening Variables. e-Jurnal Apresiasi Ekonomi. 2018; 6 (2): 92 – 102. <https://www.neliti.com/id/publications/283313/effect-of-leadership-training-and-human-resources-competency-to-employee-perform>
- [34] Mohammed Raja Abulraheem Salah. The Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity. International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research. July-2016; 5(7). <https://zenodo.org/record/3464807#.YDkJRozZ0w>
- [35] Aidah Nassazi. Effects of training on employee performance. Evidence from Uganda. The Vaasan Ammattikorkeakoulu University of Applied Science. International Business. 2013. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/EFFECTS-OF-TRAINING-ON-EMPLOYEE-PERFORMANCE.-%3A-from-Nassazi/1a07b9726d55a50a6bf112e2494abddf52bee6e4>
- [36] I Wayan Manggis, Anik Yuesti, I Ketut Setia Sapta. The Effect of Career Development and Organizational Culture Employee Performance with Motivation of Work as Intervening. Variable in Cooperation in Denpasar Village. International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review. 2018; 9(7). <http://216.10.241.171/ijcr.info/index.php/ijcr/article/view/553?articlesBySameAuthorPage=2>
- [37] Pranoto, Suharto, Subagja IK. The effect of ability and work environment on employee performance through work motivation in Pt. Insurance Bringin Sejahtera Artamakmur Jakarta. Paideuma Journal. 2020; 13(3): 114-119. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340077722_THE_EFFECT_OF_ABILITY_AND_WORK_ENVIRONMENT_TO_EMPLOYEE_PERFORMANCE_THROUGH_WORK_MOTIVATION_IN_PT_INSURANCE_BRINGIN_SEJAHTERA_ARTAMAKMUR_JAKARTA